

**A Critical Analytical Essay (Review) on
“Astropolitik: Classical Geopolitics in the Space Age”
Everett C. Dolman**

(Frank Cass Publication, London, 2002, 224pp)

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Introduction:

Astropolitik has been the focal area of discussion in strategy since Yuri Gagarin, a soviet cosmonaut and pilot firstly walked in Near-Earth orbit of outer-space travelling by Vostok-1 in 1961 (Dolman 2002, 110). Later, Neil Armstrong, Michael Collins and Buzz Aldrin explored the surface of the Moon for the first time in 1969 (NASA Web, 2019). The then government of the USA has explored the Moon, a crucial part of Space, as a counter to the Soviet-led Space exploration (Anantatmula, 2013). However, the cold competition in the Cold War made the two superpowers- The USA and the Soviet Union- more desperate and ambitious about exploring and having more presence in Space- the next theatre of conflict (Nardon, 2007).

In this respect, “Astropolitik: Classical Geopolitics in the Space Age”, written by Everett Carl Dolman, is a remarkable work on the geopolitical importance of Space that the author explicated through the lenses of grand theories such as Realism, Liberalism, Sea Power Theory of Alfred Thayer Mahan and Geopolitical theories of Mackinder, Spykman and Friedrich Ratzel (Dolman 2002, 6). This book, however, is one of the four books that are published in “Cass Series: Strategy and History” edited by Colin Gray and Williamson Murray. This is the fourth book of the series written by Everett Carl Dolman, an American Professor of Comparative Strategy and Military Studies at the ACSC (the US Air Force’s Air Command and Staff College).

The book, titled ‘Astropolitik: Classical Geopolitics in the Space Age’, has been published in 2002 by FRANK CASS PUBLICATION. This book mainly sheds light on ‘spacepower theory’ based on the theoretical standpoints and geopolitical frameworks of Space power and highlights the notions of cooperation and political unity in space. The series editors viewed Space as the theatre of ‘international terrestrial conflict’ which is named ‘Astropolitik’. From Cold War to the contemporary war and conflict such as the Ukraine crisis, every single juncture marks some crucial developments in strategy where Space is the inevitable theatre of conflict. Despite having more discussions on Realist and Liberal standpoints regarding

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astropolitics, the Author has tried to give rise to the new ideas of astropolitics which he counts as ‘classical geopolitics’.

To delineate the whole concept by following scholarly and theoretical works of Realism, Liberalism, Sea Power, Land Power and many grand strategies, the author has brought out the five crucial relevant chapters in the book apart from the introduction and conclusion. The author established a chronological portrayal of the implications of Realism, Liberalism, Geopolitics, Astropolitics and Astrostrategy in the Space-Power politics which work, though, seems to be more theoretical rather than being practical and pragmatic, this will command the “high frontier” (Tannenwald, 2004)

Core Thesis of the Book:

By the time, ‘military space strategy’ has been a considerable part of the superpowers’ - the US and the Soviet Union- war strategies focused on controversies related to ‘ballistic missile defence and anti-satellite weapons (E. Dolman, 2002, pp. 38, 56).’ In contrast to the development, in strategy, the importance of ‘space power’ has surpassed the many other correlated strategic developments in war and conflict (Sheehan, 2007). The work of Everett Dolman on Astropolitik provides the readers with an analysis of the potential and evolution of the ‘high frontier’ of Space as a crucial strategic environment which, in this scholarly work, is backed by geopolitical theories (Command and Vandenberg 2005).

This book has made a breakthrough contribution to the infant and underdeveloped field of the ‘Spacepower theory’ presenting a new but bright trajectory for further thoughts in the strategic environment (Bowen, 2017). The editor of the Series, Colin Gray suggests that this book is a blend of strategic theory, orbital mechanics and international history. This theory as well as a history-based book on space-power consists of several esoteric, cabalistic and significant chapters that shed light on beginning a new academic discourse in strategic studies.

The very initial chapter of the book along with the introduction, however, offers a wide-ranging and informative review of those military developments and geostrategic writings that are compatible and correlated with the strategic environment of outer space and space power. The contribution of Morgenthau to classical realism and Kenneth Waltz to Neo-realism as well as the continuations of Halford Mackinder, Nicholas Spykman and Friedrich Ratzel in Geopolitics have also been aptly coined in explicating the significance of outer space. The classical theories of geopolitics have been employed in these chapters that lay bare the precise congruous discussion on Astropolitics.

The subsequent chapter, by contrast, has mainly focused on the technical manuals related to space physics that provide a concisely focused examination of demarcations and Astro-mechanical properties of outer space. Dolman also has portrayed Astropolitik as a realm of realpolitik that models the astropolitical environment as the next theatre of power politics while he also exhibited that the Liberal state like the US has the duty to lead outer space.

In the next couple of chapters, the author has brought forth the reconciliation of the powerful states in establishing the cooperative ‘outer space regime’ during the middle of the Cold War, marked by the Outer Space Treaty in 1967. Before delineating the ‘then and now’ of the outer

space regime, Dolman elucidated the realist lens of seeing space as an apt strategic environment for dominating the next phase of the conflict.

The author, in the final chapter, has not forgotten to advocate in favour of the US in advancing the astrostrategy for the efficacious hegemony of the United States space supremacy. Recommending policies and the ways of applications, Dolman exhibits a unique trajectory of astrostrategy. In conclusion of the impeccable work on astrostrategy, the author upheld the liberal stance of the US in playing a leading role regarding space power. He argued, 'as the great liberal democracy in the contemporary time, the US is preferentially endowed with the duty of guiding the whole humanity in outer space, monitoring the misuse of the realm and ensuring the legitimate part of its spoils (E. Dolman, 2002, p. 181).'

The Cogency of Astrostrategic Rivalry in Outer Space:

Although the core thesis of the work is considerably based on the theoretical works of the nineteenth and twentieth century on geopolitics, this scholarly work highly focuses on human command and conflict in outer space. Following that, the realist viewpoint of state competition regarding outer space policy has been palpable for years (Al-Rodhan, 2012). The early twentieth century marks a breakthrough rise of geopolitical clashes among the great powers- the US, UK, Germany, France and Russia- following realist dogma in this regard, whereas the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries underwent radical changes in technological advancements which results in a clash in space exploration giving rise to spacepower rivalry (Lieberman, 2020).

Colin Gray, in respect of *Astropolitik* and astropolitics, talks about a significant unity to all types of strategic developments in all periods of history as nothing exigent, related to the function and nature of war, changes. Gray also argued that strategy is made of force and impendence of force for the sake of the policy ends (E. Dolman, 2002, p. 02) (KLEIN, 2011). His definition, however, is widely accepted as it accords with the Clausewitzian dictum which states that the 'war is the continuation of politics (political discourse) by other (extreme) means (force)' (Gray, 2002). Therefore, the offensive realist paradigm that illustrates fear and violence in an excessive manner cannot be detached from *Astropolitik*.

The innovative study of Dolman suggests a more pragmatic scheme of *realpolitik* in outer space. *Astropolitik* in spacepower competition has been the focal issue for the last couple of decades whither he argues that the rhetoric of political unity and cooperation had never been unfeigned (Sheldon, 2010). Therefore, states are continuously installing new strategies intending to secure dominance in outer space (Harrison, 2013). Not only the United States and Russia but also the other great powers, major powers even middle and mini-power states are also endorsing different strategies regarding space. Dolman's work gave rise to spacepower theory by following classical theories of geopolitics and sea power of Mahan, Ratzel and Spykeman offered valid insights into the astrostrategic environment of outer space (Swilley, 2011).

***Astropolitik* from a Critical Lens:**

Spacepower theory has been one of the robust cores of power politics among the great power rivals since the early phase of the Cold War (Sheldon, 2010). Hence, astropolitics and

Astropolitik is not a new notion in strategic rivalries. However, the author has successfully ascertained the theory of spacepower and remarkably advocated that the role of the United States in outer space must be assertive and the superpower should direct all other states in exploring and using the resources and advantages of outer space with cooperative and united way following international norms to this respect (E. Dolman, 2002, p. 175). The author explicated the works of Immanuel Kant and Michael Doyle in order to exhibit a liberal and ideal spectrum of space power distribution where the US is the default leader in power exercising (E. Dolman, 2002, pp. 03, 25).

By contrast, at one point of argument, the author delineated the ideas of political unity and cooperation as rhetoric and argued that they have never been 'genuine'. Along with Admiral Mahan's sea power theory, Mackinder and Spykman's theories of heartland and rimland and Ratzel's theories of lebensraum and organic states theories have been exerted in developing the concept of spacepower theory (Dolman 2008). Therefore, this is obscure whether the author's writing gives a grounded theory or not. In Dolman's 'Astropolitik' he followed the deductive method rather than following the inductive method in his scholarly work.

Everett Dolman, in his writing, was remarkably in favour of the liberal internationalism of Immanuel Kant where he proposed an idealistic approach to utilise outer space based on cooperative treaties like the Outer Space Treaty (OST) in 1967 (Dunnett, 2016). In contrast to this argument, outer space is seen as the next theatre of conflict in which every great power rivals are interested to exert their own policies. The realpolitik of space like the realpolitik of geography has been the core issue that led all the powerful states to sketch a new strategy (Astrostrategy) in respect of spacepower competition (Meijer, 2009).

Concluding Remarks:

Though the author has described many distinct issues in the writing regarding astropolitics and spacepower theory, he comparably depicted the crux and issues of competition and cooperation (E. Dolman, 2002, p. 164). Later, he also recapitulated the future scenarios of astropolitics and astrostrategy and their implication and substance in world politics. In the military arena and this era of globalisation, space and spacepower remains a state-dominated and competitive realm (Berryman, 2003). However, nowadays, cheaper, versatile and durable air-breathing technologies are making some sort of challenges against space-based domination (Henry, 2003). From the perspective of the Mahanian concept, air-breathing brown-water flee of Global Hawk UAVs, Predator and more sophisticated surveillance equipment will supplement the costly blue-water fleet of unmanned satellites of space (Berryman, 2003).

However, Dolman aptly pointed out that the US dominance in outer space which is one of the six operational goals of the US military. Besides, he in detail discussed the whole US military trajectory of space dominance based on the strategies of the US National Command Plan (2002) and US Strategic Command. National Security Strategy prefers the US should not give any room to any foreign power to have its reign in outer space with a more presence than the US (Berryman, 2003; E. Dolman, 2002, p. 175). This rivalry has been more palpable among the great powers since the Soviet Union fell in 1991. From that perspective, the contribution of Everett C. Dolman and his vision of Astropolitik are going to command the 'high frontier' and open up new strategic realms (Berryman, 2003).

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